

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF RECENT NEOLOGISMS

Inomova Durdona

UZSWLU, Master's degree student

Aliqulov Abduhakim Ganievich

Karshi State University, Teacher at the Department of Linguistics

Abstract: Nowadays, the English dialect is the foremost broadly utilized dialect of communication around the world. Lingos are always changing and advancing. There are different components that back this planning, counting coined words. Changes inside a lingo happen at distinctive levels of discourse, morpheme, lexicon, sentence structure. The three fundamental layers are the ones that are most vulnerable to alter and are, in reality, clear to a specific era.

Key words: lexicon, target dialect, coined words, social environment, academic standards

Introduction

As science and development progress, a few of the unused words will show up in English lingos. Dialect lexicon is always changing at an ever-increasing rate. Advance advancement of lingos will bring advance at different levels, for case in lexical hypothesis. One of these progresses is the coined marvel. The displayed papers are committed to cutting-edge English coined words and their word arrangement. Dialect is the cycle of human development that to begin with brings around social, political, and other changes in human life.

Neologisms (from the Greek neo = "advanced" + logos = "word") can be recently coined words, terms, or phrases-applies to everyday unused concepts. Or translate more prepared terms into more terms An overview of the latest Lingo. Coined words are especially welcomed in an innovative social environment. It is by definition "cutting" that is useful in recognizing developments, untapped wonders,

or ancient remorse, including coined words, so it is often possible to track specifically to a particular person, transmission, duration, or event. The term "coined word" was coined in 1800, so at some point in the early 19th century, the word "coined word" itself was coined. A coined word may also refer to an existing word or state that has been attributed to a modern meaning [22; 115].

Discussion

Neologisms and concepts are presented before social or political change, transformation and development. Many of them are "enemy of the people" (transformation of France and Russia) and "bourgeois nationalism" (bourgeois nationalism). Communist Soviet Union), "The Final Settlement of Uden Frage" (Right-wing Germany), "Iron Curtain", "Perestroika" (Gorbachev's change), etc. All of these terms were declared and then comparative results were obtained. Here are a few illustrations of neologisms that are finding their way into modern-day English language.

Examples of Prevalent Culture Neologisms:

Tebowing: depiction of a pious triumph position determined from NFL quarterback Tim Tebow.

Brangelina: utilized to allude to supercouple Brad Pitt and Angelina Jolie.

Muffin best: This alludes to the (regularly unattractive) roll of fat that shows up on best of pants that highlight a moo waist.

BFF: Stands for best companions until the end of time. Utilized to state how near you're to another individual.

Chilax: To calm down or relax, it could be a slang term used when somebody is beginning to urge uptight almost something that's happening.

Racne: Skin break out found on a woman's chest.

Election Campaign Neologisms:

Republican'ts – The 49 percent of Republicans who, in a later overview, were incapable to clarify the meaning of their party's initials “GOP.”

Mitthead – An person who always changes his political positions to suit his gathering of people and objectives,” Moon-basing – The act of a candidate or surrogate offhandedly proposing a arrangement so over the top that it essentially hurts the candidate's electability.

Here are cases of Washington Post neologisms:

1. Coffee (n.), the individual upon whom one coughs.
2. Floored (adj.), horrified over how much weight you've got gained.
3. Resign (v.), to provide up all trust of ever having a level stomach.
4. Esplanade (v.), to endeavor an clarification whereas drunk.
5. Willy-nilly (adj.), impotent.
6. Careless (adj.), portrays a condition in which you absentmindedly answer the entryway in your nightgown.

The latest coined words, then collected from various social media sources, are directly related to all the characteristics of modern wonders and the emergence of ideas in our standard of living. Negology is one of the many questions of interpretation without standardized regulation. In reports, coined words are very common for the ability and control of information compression and expressiveness. You need to be an interpreter. Translate them into the target dialect using very complex thoughts that include many variables such as: types of content, creative practices, academic standards, and traditions that are recognizable to the reader of a particular society.

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